

Factors Hindering the Effective Integration of Almajiri Schools in Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools into formal education in Niger state. The study employed descriptive survey research. The population of the study consisted of Community Based Management Committees (CBMC) members, Mallams/teachers, and learners/pupils from 24 Integrated Islamiyya and Tsanaya schools in Niger state. Six (6) Local Government Areas were selected randomly; two from each senatorial zone. The total population of the respondents is forty-four thousand six hundred (44,800). This comprised of 2,600 for CBMC (6%), 2,000 for teachers (4%), and 40,200 for pupils (90%). A simple of 384 respondents (23 for CBMC, 15 for teachers, and 346 for pupils) was drawn proportionately sampling technique from twenty-four (24) schools. Three research questions guided the study and inventory on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools was used as the instrument for data collection. The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation with 2.50 point as threshold set for decision. The findings of the study showed that non-availability of food for the Almajirai to concentrate on their school work, non-availability of first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai in schools and lack of adequate classroom accommodations and learning facilities to provide conducive teaching and learning were factors identified as hindrance to integration of the Almajiri schools in Niger state. The study recommended school feeding programme, provision of first aid equipment, adequate classroom accommodation, learning and recreational facilities, and provision of grants and financial support, among others, for effective integration of the Almajiri schools in Niger State.

Keywords: Factors Hindering, Integration, Almajiri Schools

Introduction

The word Almajiri is derived from an Arabic word 'Al-Muhajir'; meaning a seeker of Islamic knowledge. From the Islamic perspective, the word 'Al-muhajirun' was first used by the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) on those of his companions who migrated with him for the sake of Islam from Makka to Madina. However, the name Al-Muhajirun later came to refer to those who seek for knowledge and move from one place to another in search of knowledge (Goodluck & Juliana, 2017; Taiwo, 2013). Against this background, the word Almajiri was borrowed by the Hausa language which refers to the immigrant children in search of Qur'anic Education which is considered as the pre-primary and primary levels of traditional Islamic Education (Ali, 2022 & Goodluck & Juliana, 2017).

In Northern Nigeria, Almajiri refers to children sent from their homes and entrusted into the care of an Islamic scholar called 'Malam' (teacher), to learn the Islamic Education (Ayuba, 2009 & Yusha'u, et al., 2013). Therefore, the Almajiri education system in this context, refers to a traditional method of acquiring and memorizing the Glorious Qur'an in the Northern part of the country; where boys at their tender ages are sent out by their parents or guardians to other villages, towns or cities for the sake of learning Qur'an education under a knowledgeable Islamic scholar called Malam (Yusha'u, et al., 2013). Hence, the term Almajirai is the plural of the word 'Almajiri', which refers to pupils of traditional Qur'anic schools also called as Tsangaya schools who are mostly school-aged children drawn from rural communities to urban areas with the intention of acquiring Qur'anic knowledge.

Ayuba (2009) and Idriss and Hamza (2021) described Almajirci (the process of acquiring Islamic education) as a semi-formal system of Qur'anic education in which children mostly boys are sent by their parents to take up residence with Islamic scholars (*Malams*), for the purpose of acquiring the knowledge of Qur'an and other Islamic texts. In this respect, the Qur'anic or Islamic education in Nigeria is offered in three types of schools. The first is the traditional form, where boys (pupils) travel to distant places to learn under the tutorship of a teacher; called Malam (who himself is a product of such schools). Secondly, there are non-boarding Qur'anic schools where pupils learn for a few hours and return home. This type of

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school is commonly found in the South-western part of Nigeria. Thirdly, the Islamiyya schools that combine both the Qur'anic education and Western education.

Odumosu, et al. (2013) observed that the Almajiri school system was meant to teach children basic Islamic spiritual, moral and social values in order to enhance their sense of responsibility. It was also aimed at inculcating in them the value of caring for those in need. The original objective of the Almajiri system of education therefore was intellectual and moral training as well as life-long discipline before its subsequent adulteration with the beggary institution. Yusha'u, et al. (2013) stated that the aim and objective of the Qur'anic system of education is to produce a faithful and piety man that will be useful to the society. Thus, the Almajiri system of education is designed to train children intellectually and morally.

However, despite the salient benefits of the Almajiri school system, there are some problems associated with it. Muhammad (2010) and Teke, et al. (2022) observed the problems associated with the Almajiri schools to include: Inadequate provision of feeding, over population, lack of payment of salary, begging, enrollment of under aged, poor methods of discipline and lack of organized curriculum. Yusha'u, et al. (2013) also identified the major challenges affecting the Almajiri schools to include; unfriendly environment, over crowdedness, inadequate instructional materials, insufficient teachers and instructors, and inadequate community support to the Qur'anic schools, among others.

Consequently, the poor nature and practice of the Almajiri education system has made the general public to perceive and view it as a trend which breeds child abuse syndrome in the society. It is in view of this negative perception and circumstance surrounding the Almajiri schools that led to intervention programmes in the recent time by both local and international donors, federal, state, and local governments as well as Non-Governmental Organization (NGOs) and individuals' philanthropists to reform the system for better realization of the national goals on education. Against this backdrop, the Federal Government in 1998 made pronouncement that the Almajiri schools would be integrated into the formal system of education. To this end, the Federal Government of Nigeria through the National Council on Education (NCE) at its sitting in Enugu (2001) approved the integration of Qur'anic schools into the Universal Basic Education schools (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2002). Consequent upon this, the Almajiri Integrated Schools (AIS) across the country as one of the interventions of government strategies to curtail the menace of street begging, child abuse and out of school children were established (Paiko, 2013).

In April, 2016, the government of Niger State set a committee to look into the Almajiri and begging syndrome in the state. The outcome of the committee's assignment led to a number of programmes and interventions such as training and re-training of the Malams and sensitization programmes at both urban and rural communities for the integration of the Almajiri schools in the state (Agency for Mass Education, 2021).

Contextually, integration refers to merging of the two systems of education together. That is, a combination of the Western system of education and Qur'anic system of education. Isah (2013) defined integration as the process that involves teaching literacy to learners of Qur'anic schools, at a period agreed upon between the proprietor of the schools and the facilitators without interfering in the running of the Qur'anic education programme. In this case, the two forms of education are expected to be provided hand-in-hand with the existing Qur'anic school programme.

Thus, the purpose of integrating the two systems of education is to provide educational opportunities for the Almajirai through an integrated curriculum that will promote the study of Qur'anic education and Basic Education subjects, to strengthen the ability of the learners to read, write and memorize the Qur'an so as to provide opportunities for the graduates of the schools to further their studies, to provide a conducive and organized learning environment, to provide the Almajirai with opportunities to acquire knowledge and vocational skills that will enable them to be self-reliant and useful to their communities, and to provide health, sanitary, and physical conditions and social security and welfare that ensures protection of the Almajirai from all forms of dangers and risks (Adetoro, 2012; Dukku, 2006; Mahuta, 2009; Mamman, et al., 2020; Muhammad, 2010 & Yusha'u, et al., 2013).

Although the integration policy is widely accepted by stakeholders of the Qur'anic schools, there are contentious issues which hamper its implementation. The challenges include lack of strong political will on the part of government, absence of a sustainable funding framework, scarcity of resources, inadequacy of trained teaching force, high demands of labour practices with the routines of the schools, and perceived irrelevance of curriculum content to the realities of the Almajirai and their communities (Junaid, et al., 2005 & Olutola, et al., 2021). Suleiman (2004) also outlined the hindrances to effective integration of the Almajiri schools to include inadequate classrooms, absence of sitting and writing materials, lack of textbooks and free feeding, resistance by the proprietors of the Qur'anic schools, adverse criticisms against the Almajiri system, vulnerability

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(exposure to contingencies, risks, shocks or hazards, loss of livelihood, death of a parent, acute or chronic poverty, disease, drought, flood, and stress). Other factors that affect the integration policy are poverty, social exclusion (such as denial of rights and privileges), begging and misconceptions and perceptions of Western Education as Westernization of Muslims (Adetoro, 2010; Jimba 2021; Hamza, 2009; Isiaka, 2015; Mahuta, 2009 & Odumosu, et al., 2013). Therefore, the rationale for this study is timely as its findings would be useful to government at all levels, relevant stakeholders, parents, non-governmental organizations, and well-meaning individuals to reinvigorate efforts as well as committing resources to address the challenges.

The Almajiri school system has denied the Almajirai access to formal education. This practice has rendered the Almajirai non-literate and vulnerable; as well as increased the rates of out of school children in Niger State and the country at large. The consequences may include security threats such as engaging in various social ills and unrest, thurggery, delinquent behaviour, kidnapping, banditry, and insurgencies. The Almajiri school system has also exposed the Almajirai to begging syndrome; thereby constituting a great socio-economic threat that requires research to uncover the factors that hinder effective integration of the schools as well as to proffer strategies that will minimize the challenges.

Objectives of the Study

The major purpose of this study is to investigate factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. The specific objectives therefore, include:

1. To examine the views of CBMC members on factors hindering effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State.
2. To determine the views of teachers/malams on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State.
3. To assess the views of learners/pupils on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State.

Research Questions

1. What are the views of CBMC members on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State?
2. What are the views of teachers/malams on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State?
3. What are the views of learners/pupils on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State?

Methodology

The design for this study is a descriptive survey research. It is considered appropriate because it involves the use of questionnaire on existing situation among a large number of respondents. The design was relevant because it assisted to investigate the phenomenon of Almajiri school system across a wide range of the respondents and allow for adequate and appropriate sample which the findings were generalized on the entire population. The target population of this study is all the members of Community Based Management Committees (CBMC), teachers/mallams and the learners/pupils in the Integrated Islamiyya and Tradition Qur'anic/Tsangaya schools of Niger state. There are over 15,000 Islamic and Qur'anic schools in Niger state but two hundred (200) are integrated (Niger State Agency for Mass Education, 2021). The total population of the respondents is forty-four thousand six hundred (44,600). This comprised of 2,600 for CBMC (6%), 2,000 for teachers (4%), and 40,200 for pupils (90%). The sample size of the study is 384 respondents. This was determined using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) population table for determining a sample size. The selection includes 23 CBMC members (6%), 15 teachers (4%), and 346 pupils (90%). Simple random sampling technique was used to select six (6) out of the 25 Local Government Areas in the state, and four (4) Integrated Qur'anic and Islamiyya schools were chosen from each Local Government Area; giving a total of 24 schools. A proportionate sampling technique was employed for selection of the respondents presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Population and Sample Size

S/No	Respondents	Population	Sample	Total
1.	CBMC	2,600	23	23
2.	Teachers/Malams	2,000	15	15
3.	Learners/Pupils	40,200	346	346
	Total	44,800	384	384

The instrument for collection of data in this study was titled: An inventory on factors hindering effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. This was developed by the researcher. The inventory has two (2) parts: Part one centred on the demographic data of respondents covering category of respondent (CBMC, Malams/teachers, and learners/pupils), Local

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Government Area and Senatorial zone. Part two has 10 items measuring factors hindering integration of Almajiri schools. The items were prepared on four - point's modified Likert's scale namely; Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree which were scored 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively.

The face and content validity of the instrument was ascertained by experts in Educational Psychology, Test and Measurement, and Guidance and Counselling from Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, University of Abuja, and IBB University, Lapai. Cronbach Alpha-20 method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument which had 0.80 index tested at 0.05 levels of significance.

The collection of data in this study was carried out personally by the researcher. Since the research work covered the entire state, five (5) research assistants were trained and used together with the researcher during the data collection process across twenty (24) selected Integrated Almajiri schools in three (3) Local Government Areas. The researcher also visited the State Ministry of Education, State Universal Basic Education Board and State Agency for Mass Education to collect other relevant secondary data which include total number of the schools and records of SBMC, teachers, and pupils. The data collection was by a way of focus group method which lasted for two days. The analysis of the data collected was carried out using mean and standard deviation, with 2.50 point as threshold set for decision.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the views of CBMC members on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State?

Table 2: Views of CBMC members on factors Hindering Effective Integration of Almajiri Schools (n=23)

SN	Factors Hindering Effective Integration	Mean	SD	Decision
1	The Almajiri Schools lack adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning	3.73	.659	A Factor
2	There are inadequate facilitators to teach the subjects that are integrated in to the Almajiri school curriculum	3.68	.674	A Factor
3	The Almajiri schools lack regular monitoring and supervision	3.27	.863	A Factor
4	There is no adequate security to protect the Almajiri against rituals and child-traffickers while in school	3.61	.822	A Factor
5	Inadequate provision of teaching materials has hindered the activities of the Almajiri schools.	3.57	.7630	A Factor
6	The Almajiri schools lack means of transportation to ease their programmes.	3.54	.801	A Factor
7	Inadequate funding has hindered the progress of Almajiri schools in terms of motivating facilitators and addressing school problems.	3.63	.756	A Factor
8	Food is not available for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work	3.78	.518	A Factor
9	There is no available first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in school.	3.73	.535	A Factor
10	There is the fear that government may assume the ownership of the Almajiri schools.	3.15	.728	A Factor
Total Mean Score		3.56		A Factor

The results in Table 2 indicated the mean score rating of CBMC members regarding their views of factors hindering integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. All the factors on the instrument had the mean scores above the criterion mean score of 2.50, the CBMC members perceived 'Food is not available for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work' with a mean score of 3.78 as the highest determinant hampering or hindering integration of the Almajiri schools in Niger state. This was followed by 'There is no available first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in school' and 'The Almajiri schools lack adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning. The two indicators had the mean scores of 3.73. Nevertheless, the factor 'there is the fear that government may assume the ownership of the Almajiri schools'

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had the least mean score of 3.15. Based on the cluster mean score of 3.56, it was concluded that CBMC members perceived generally that the factors discussed above had impact on the integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state.

Research Question 2

What are the views of teachers/malams on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State?

Table 3: Views of Teachers/Malams on factors Hindering Effective Integration of Almajiri Schools (n=15)

SN	Factors Hindering Effective Integration	Mean	SD	Decision
1	The Almajiri Schools lack adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning	3.51	.822	A Factor
2	There are inadequate facilitators to teach the subjects that are integrated in to the Almajiri school curriculum	3.43	.819	A Factor
3	The Almajiri schools lack regular monitoring and supervision	3.35	.967	A Factor
4	There is no adequate security to protect the Almajiri against rituals and child-traffickers while in school	3.36	1.025	A Factor
5	Inadequate provision of teaching materials has hindered the activities of Almajiri schools.	3.31	.898	A Factor
6	The Almajiri schools lack means of transportation to ease their programmes	3.28	.967	A Factor
7	Inadequate funding has hindered the progress of Almajiri schools in terms of motivating facilitators and addressing school problems.	3.40	.959	A Factor
8	Food is not available for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work	3.70	.597	A Factor
9	There is no available first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in school	3.60	.597	A Factor
10	There is the fear that government may assume the ownership of the Almajiri schools.	3.21	.887	A Factor
Total Mean Score		3.42		A Factor

The findings in Table 3 showed the mean score rating of Teachers/Malams regarding their views of factors hindering effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. Although all the factors on the scale had the mean scores above the criterion mean score of 2.50, the Teachers/Malams perceived 'Food is not available for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work' with a mean score of 3.70 as the highest determinant of factors hindering integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. This was followed by 'There is no available first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in school' with a mean score of 3.60, and 'The Almajiri schools lack adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning' with a mean of 3.51. Nevertheless, there is the fear that government may assume the ownership of the Almajiri schools had the least mean score of 3.21. Based on the cluster mean score of 3.42, it was concluded that Teachers/ Malams perceived generally that the above factors had impact on the integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state.

Research Question 3

What are the views of learners/pupils on factors hindering the effective integration of Almajiri schools in Niger State?

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Table 4: Learners'/Pupils' Views on factors Hindering the Effective Integration of Almajiri Schools (n=346)

SN	Factors Hindering Effective Integration	Mean	SD	Decision
1	The Almajiri Schools lack adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning	3.64	.589	A factor
2	There are inadequate facilitators to teach the subjects that are integrated in to the Almajiri school curriculum	3.61	.571	A factor
3	The Almajiri schools lack regular monitoring and supervision	3.35	.772	A factor
4	There is no adequate security to protect the Almajiri against rituals and child-traffickers while in school	3.54	.711	A factor
5	Inadequate provision of teaching materials has hindered the activities of Almajiri schools.	3.53	.649	A factor
6	The Almajiri schools lack means of transportation to ease their programmes	3.53	.649	A factor
7	Inadequate funding has hindered the progress of Almajiri schools in terms of motivating facilitators and addressing school problems.	3.63	.638	A factor
8	Food is not available for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work	3.68	.577	A factor
9	There is no available first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in school	3.68	.552	A factor
10	There is the fear that government may assume the ownership of the Almajiri schools.	3.24	.880	A factor
Total Mean Score		3.54		A factor

The data in Table 4 indicated the mean score rating of learners/pupils regarding their perception of factors hampering/hindering integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. Although all the factors on the instrument had the mean scores above the criterion mean score of 2.50, the learners/pupils perceived 'Food is not available for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work' and There is no available first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in school both with mean scores of 3.68 as the highest determinant hampering integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state. This is followed by 'The Almajiri Schools lack adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning' with a mean of 3.64. However, there is the fear that government may assume the ownership of the Almajiri schools had the least mean score of 3.24. Based on the cluster mean score of 3.54, it was concluded that learners/pupils perceived generally that the factors had impact on the integration of Almajiri schools in Niger state.

Discussion of Findings

The findings in Table 1, 2 and 3 indicated that lack of food for the Almajirai to concentrate on their work was a major factor hampering integration of the Almajiri schools with highest mean scores for the responses of CBMC members, teachers/malams and learners or pupils as (3.78, 3.70 and 3.68) respectively. This finding was in agreement with the studies of Goodluck and Juliana (2017), Hamza (2009), Olutola, et al. (2020), and Yusha'u, et. al. (2013) which found that inadequate feeding of the Almajirai is responsible for their roaming about and begging for food. The finding on lack of adequate accommodation for conducive teaching and learning materials and non-availability of first aid and medical services to provide treatment for the sick Almajirai while in schools corroborated with the study findings of Ayuba (2009), Fahm, Azeez, Imam-Fulani, Mejabi, Faruk, Abdulrahman, and Surajudeen-Bakinde (2022), Isiaka (2015), Mohammed (2010), Teke, Khalid, and Katami (2022), and Suleman (2004) which posited that inadequate classroom accommodation have turned the Almajirai vulnerable to political thugs and child traffickers, as well as victims of insurgencies. Absence of classroom accommodation and parental care has also exposed the Almajirai to the risk of contagious diseases, dirty faces, crusty skin, and bare feet (Abdullahi, 2011; Idriss & Hamzah, 2021; Sule, 2014; and Yahaya, 2007). Consequently, the unfriendly and poor environmental nature of the Almajiri schools showed a reason why there is congestion or overcrowding and insecurity among them (Adetoro, 2010; Jimba (2021; Lawal, 2013; Mohammed, 2010; & Yusha'u, et al., 2013).

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In another development, the finding of this study which indicated as factor the non-availability of first aid and medical services to provide medical services for the Almajirai while in school agreed with the study outcomes of Ali (2022), Teke, et al. (2022); Odumosu, et al. (2013); and Yahaya (2007) which found that absence of required medical care for the Almajirai is responsible for their developmental challenges; including health hazards, exposure to contingencies and stress, insecurity, and truncated life. It is therefore expedient for government at all levels, civil societies, non-governmental organizations and individual philanthropists to extend humanitarian services to the Almajiri schools in order to fast-track measures toward combating their prevalence challenges.

Conclusion

The integration of Almajiri schools is a good step toward creating access to basic education. However, the challenges and obstacles involved in the policy are enormous. Hence, this study has delved into some of the impending issues that serve as hindrance for realizing the goals of the integration programme in Niger State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. School feeding programme by government at all levels should be introduced in Almajiri schools to boost their interest and to facilitate their concentration on school work for better academic performance.
2. First Aid equipment should be provided at the Almajiri schools by the CBMC, Parents' Teachers' Association, and Non-Governmental associations to provide medical services in order to improve the environmental hygiene and safety of the schools.
3. Government, civil organizations or individuals should take the responsibility of providing affordable medical care and treatment for the sick Almajirai while in schools to guarantee their healthy conditions.
4. Building of classroom accommodations and provision of learning and recreational facilities should be made a priority through intervention funds from governments, international donors and community self-help projects to provide conducive teaching and learning environment at the Almajiri schools.
5. Adequate sensitization and enlightenment should be mounted to educate public and key stakeholders in education sector on the relevance of integrating the Almajiri schools into Basic Education programme to improve the level of public access to education.

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